

Impacts of relay and direct links at destinations in full-duplex non-orthogonal multiple access system

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ABSTRACT

In this study, one of effective methods of multiple access, namely non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA), is investigated. Such NOMA scheme can be worked with signal processing at downlink side. As such, the base station sends mixed signals of two signals to destinations. A near user could be a relay to forward the signal to the distant user by leveraging benefits of full-duplex mode which allows relay to transmit and receive signals in the same time. For simple analysis, the two-user approach and fixed power allocation factors are implemented. We also derive formulas of the outage probability of two users (near-user and far-user) to indicate fairness and emphasize the role of the near user as a relay. This considered NOMA system adopts transmission with Nakagami- m fading channel. As a further metric, throughput is considered under the impacts of key system parameters. The transmit signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) at the base station make influences the performance of two users significantly as observation indicated in our simulation results. These results are confirmed by matching Monte-Carlo with the theoretical simulations.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA) has been the leading applications to develop services with high demand of bandwidth efficiency [1]-[3]. More benefits from NOMA are better fairness and improved energy efficiency [4], [5]. The multiple users are multiplexed in the context of NOMA at the same time and frequency. Compared with conventional orthogonal multiple access (OMA), more users are provided with the superimposing signals processed at the transmitter while successive interference cancellation (SIC) is employed at the receiver [6], [7]. By exploiting the distances from users to the base station (BS) in the NOMA system, the two kinds of users are classified such as the near user and the far user. Unfortunately, the existence of the worse performance of the far user since long-distance transmission as results reported in [8]. To guarantee fairness among many users employing NOMA scheme, the far users should be allocated more power while less power is assigned to near users. In particular, the fixed power allocation approach was adopted to guarantee the performance of the fairness and processing load. This scheme will provide acceptable quality-of-service (QoS) requirements regardless of feedback/header information [8]. It is in high demand to implement higher coverage for wireless systems and a cooperative transmission approach is recommended to employ NOMA to improve the performance of two users [9]-[13].

The previous studies regarding the wireless system employing half-duplex (HD) transmission show

lower bandwidth efficiency since these approaches cannot transmit and receive simultaneously. At HD, less bandwidth efficiency is required by two time slots are used to transmit signal from the base station to destination via a relay. Recently, to overcome this problem, full-duplex (FD) based NOMA-assisted systems are studied [14]-[23]. The downlink cooperative NOMA systems employ compress-and-forward (CF)-based FD relay to improve transmissions [14]. To specify the quality, the achievable rate region is examined in the proposed technique. In the scenario of [15], to allow BS to communicate with destinations, an FD-NOMA architecture was considered for a downlink cellular network and a dedicated FD relay benefits to cell-edge users. A network-coded cooperative NOMA (NC-CNOMA) strategy is studied, in which users implement physical-layer network coding (PNC) to demodulate signals [16]. Considering the main simulation results in terms of outage probability, the NC-CNOMA scheme shows high advantages compared with the conventional cooperative NOMA system [16].

Zhang *et al.* [17], a cell-center user operates as an FD relay to forward signal to a distant user as the work presented in [16]. As the main result, [17] explored the optimal power allocation and optimal outage probability satisfies at proper applications related to NOMA scheme. The authors proved the closed-form formulas of outage probability and ergodic sum-rate [17]. The authors in [18] examined the performance of downlink NOMA by exploiting the average block error rate (BLER) and such a system is suitable for short-packet communication networks. Since stochastic geometry is deployed in a system relying on Nakagami- m fading channels, which corresponds to the locations of NOMA users and these users obey uniform distribution in a disc [19]. The authors studied theoretically the analytical formulas for average BLER in [19]. By treating Nakagami- m fading channels, a spectrum-efficient scheme is proposed for the NOMA system. The BS sends signals directly to a cell-center user (CCU). By achieving a relay and the CCU, they derived a formula for performance analysis of a cell-edge user (CEU) [20]. Motivated recent studies [20]-[23], we exploit main system performance metric for FD-NOMA.

2. SYSTEM MODEL

As illustration in Figure 1, a downlink NOMA needs a robust transmission by allowing one base station (BS) and two NOMA users (D_1 and D_2) to work together. One of possible case is the far user is able to connect directly with BS, i.e. the far user D_2 needs support from the near user D_1 . $|g_1|^2, |g_2|^2, |g_3|^2, |g_f|^2$ are considered to follow exponential distribution, i.e. $\lambda_{g_i}, i \in \{1, 2, 3, f\}$. The received signal at D_1 can be given by [24]:

Figure 1. System model

$$y_{D_1} = g_1 \left(\sqrt{\alpha_1 P_S} x_1 + \sqrt{\alpha_2 P_S} x_2 \right) + g_f \sqrt{P_{D_1}} x_f + \eta_{D_1}, \quad (1)$$

where P_S, P_{D_1} is denoted as the normalized transmission powers at the BS, D_1 and D_2 . x_1, x_2 are the signals for D_1, D_2 . α_1, α_2 are the corresponding power allocation coefficients, we assume that $\alpha_1 < \alpha_2$ with $\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 = 1$. The received signal to interference plus noise ratio (SINR) at D_1 to detect x_2 is written as:

$$\gamma_{D_2 \rightarrow D_1} = \frac{\alpha_2 \rho_S |g_1|^2}{\alpha_1 \rho_S |g_1|^2 + \rho_1 |g_f|^2 + 1} \quad (2)$$

where $\rho = \rho_S = \rho_1 = \frac{P_S}{N_0}$ is transmit SNR.

By exploiting SIC, a noise term is eliminated to examine new form of the received SINR at D_1 (corresponding to detect x_1) is written as:

$$\gamma_{D_1} = \frac{\alpha_1 \rho_S |g_1|^2}{\rho_1 |g_f|^2 + 1} \tag{3}$$

the received signal at D_2 can be written as [24]:

$$y_{D_2} = g_3 \left(\sqrt{\alpha_1 P_S} x_1 + \sqrt{\alpha_2 P_S} x_2 \right) + g_2 \sqrt{P_1} x_2 + \eta_{D_2} \tag{4}$$

considering other link D_2 (direct link) the received signal can be computed as [24]:

$$y_{D_2} = g_3 \left(\sqrt{\alpha_1 P_S} x_1 + \sqrt{\alpha_2 P_S} x_2 \right) + \eta_{D_2} \tag{5}$$

by computing SINR at D_2 , x_2 could be detected and SINR is formulated by:

$$\gamma_{D_2,1} = \frac{\alpha_2 \rho_S |g_3|^2}{\alpha_1 \rho_S |g_3|^2 + 1} \tag{6}$$

at user D_2 , x_2 could be detected after signal x_1 as following SINR:

$$\gamma_{D_2,2} = \rho_1 |g_2|^2 \tag{7}$$

by considering direct and relay links D_1 to D_2 have more chances to communicate with the BS. Allowing maximal ratio combining deployed at D_2 . Obtaining MRC, the received SINR at D_2 are described respectively as:

$$\gamma_{D_2}^{MRC} = \rho_1 |g_2|^2 + \frac{\alpha_2 \rho_S |g_3|^2}{\alpha_1 \rho_S |g_3|^2 + 1} \tag{8}$$

the PDF and CDF of Nakagami- m fading distribution are given by:

$$f_{|g_i|^2}(x) = \frac{x^{m_{g_i}-1} e^{-\frac{x}{\beta_{g_i}}}}{\Gamma(m_{g_i}) \beta_{g_i}^{m_{g_i}}} \tag{9}$$

and:

$$F_{|g_i|^2}(x) = 1 - e^{-\frac{x}{\beta_{g_i}}} \sum_{n=0}^{m_{g_i}-1} \frac{x^n}{n! \beta_{g_i}^n} \tag{10}$$

where $\beta_{g_i} \triangleq \frac{\lambda_{g_i}}{m_{g_i}}$ with λ_{g_i} and $m_{g_i} = m$ represent the mean and integer fading factor.

3. OUTAGE PROBABILITIES FOR TWO NOMA USERS

3.1. Outage probability of D_1

The near user D_1 employing FD mode and it meets outage probability as (11) [24]:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{OP}_{D_1} &= \Pr(\gamma_{D_2 \rightarrow D_1} < \gamma_{th,2}, \gamma_{D_1} < \gamma_{th,1}) \\ &= 1 - \Pr(\gamma_{D_2 \rightarrow D_1} > \gamma_{th,2}, \gamma_{D_1} > \gamma_{th,1}), \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

where $\gamma_{th,1} = 2^{R_1} - 1$, $\gamma_{th,2} = 2^{R_2} - 1$, R_1, R_2 are the needed target rates of corresponding users D_1, D_2 . From 2 and 3, we have as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{OP}_{D_1} &= 1 - \Pr \left(\frac{\alpha_2 \rho_S |g_1|^2}{\alpha_1 \rho_S |g_1|^2 + \rho_1 |g_f|^2 + 1} \geq \gamma_{th,2}, \frac{\alpha_1 \rho_S |g_1|^2}{\rho_1 |g_f|^2 + 1} \geq \gamma_{th,1} \right) \\ &= 1 - \int_0^\infty \int_{\xi_1(\rho_1 x + 1)}^\infty f_{|g_f|^2}(x) f_{|g_1|^2}(y) dx dy \\ &= \sum_{n_1=0}^\infty \sum_{n_2=0}^{m_{g_1} + n_1} \binom{m_{g_1} + n_1}{n_2} \frac{(-1)^{n_1} \left(\frac{\rho_1 \xi_1}{\beta_{g_1}}\right)^{n_2} \left(\frac{\xi_1}{\beta_{g_1}}\right)^{m_{g_1} + n_1 - n_2} \Gamma(m_{g_f} + n_2)}{n_1! (m_{g_1} + n_1) \Gamma(m_{g_1}) \Gamma(m_{g_f})} \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

where $\xi_1 \triangleq \max \left(\frac{\gamma_{th,2}}{\alpha_2 \rho_S - \alpha_1 \rho_S \gamma_{th,2}}, \frac{\gamma_{th,1}}{\alpha_1 \rho_S} \right)$.

3.2. Outage probability of D_2 with direct link

The complex case of the far user relies on the ability of signal detection at the near user. Then we compute the outage probability of D_2 as [24]:

$$\mathcal{OP}_{D_2}^{DL} = \underbrace{\Pr(\gamma_{D_2}^{MRC} < \gamma_{th,2}, \gamma_{D_2 \rightarrow D_1} > \gamma_{th,2})}_{\triangleq \Theta_1} + \underbrace{\Pr(\gamma_{D_2 \rightarrow D_1} < \gamma_{th,2}, \gamma_{D_2,1} < \gamma_{th,2})}_{\triangleq \Theta_2} \tag{13}$$

by definition, Θ_1 can be calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned} \Theta_1 &\triangleq \Pr(\gamma_{D_2}^{MRC} < \gamma_{th,2}, \gamma_{D_2 \rightarrow D_1} > \gamma_{th,2}) \\ &= \underbrace{\Pr(\gamma_{D_2}^{MRC} < \gamma_{th,2})}_{\triangleq \Xi_1} \underbrace{\Pr(\gamma_{D_2 \rightarrow D_1} > \gamma_{th,2})}_{\triangleq \Xi_2} \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

in which, Ξ_1 can be calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned} \Xi_1 &\triangleq \Pr(\gamma_{D_2}^{MRC} < \gamma_{th,2}) \\ &= \Pr \left(|g_2|^2 < \frac{\gamma_{th,2}}{\rho_1} - \frac{\alpha_2 |g_3|^2}{\alpha_1 \rho_S |g_3|^2 + 1}, |g_3|^2 < \underbrace{\frac{\gamma_{th,2}}{\rho_{D_1} (\alpha_2 - \alpha_1 \gamma_{th,2})}}_{\triangleq \psi_1} \right) \\ &= \int_0^{\psi_1} \frac{x^{m_{g_3} - 1}}{\Gamma(m_{g_3}) \beta_{g_3}^{m_{g_3}}} e^{-\frac{x}{\beta_{g_3}}} dx \\ &\quad - \frac{e^{-\frac{\gamma_{th,2}}{\rho_1 \beta_{g_2}}}}{\Gamma(m_{g_3}) \beta_{g_3}^{m_{g_3}}} \int_0^{\psi_1} x^{m_{g_3} - 1} e^{-\frac{x}{\beta_{g_3}}} e^{\frac{\alpha_2 x}{\beta_{g_2} (\alpha_1 \rho_S x + 1)}} \sum_{n=0}^{m_{g_2} - 1} \frac{1}{n! \beta_{g_2}^n} \left(\frac{\gamma_{th,2}}{\rho_1} - \frac{\alpha_2 x}{\alpha_1 \rho_S x + 1} \right)^n dx \\ &= \frac{\gamma(m_{g_3}, \frac{\psi_1}{\beta_{g_3}})}{\Gamma(m_{g_3})} - \sum_{n=0}^{m_{g_2} - 1} \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} \frac{e^{-\frac{\gamma_{th,2}}{\rho_1 \beta_{g_2}} \psi_2}}{n! \beta_{g_2}^n \Gamma(m_{g_3}) \beta_{g_3}^{m_{g_3}}} \left(-\frac{\alpha_2}{\alpha_1 \rho_S x + 1} \right)^k \left(\frac{\gamma_{th,2}}{\rho_1} \right)^{n-k} \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

where:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \psi_2 &\triangleq \int_0^{\psi_1} x^\mu e^{-\frac{x}{\beta_{g3}}} e^{\frac{\alpha_2 x}{\beta_{g2}(\alpha_1 \rho_S x + 1)}} dx \\
 &= \alpha_1 \rho_S \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_1 \rho_S}\right)^\mu \int_1^{\alpha_1 \rho_S \psi_1 + 1} (y-1)^\mu e^{-\frac{y-1}{\alpha_1 \rho_S \beta_{g3}}} e^{\frac{\alpha_2 (y-1)}{\alpha_1 \rho_S \beta_{g2} y}} dy \\
 &= \alpha_1 \rho_S \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_1 \rho_S}\right)^\mu \sum_{n_1=0}^{\mu} \binom{\mu}{n_1} (-1)^{\mu-n_1} \int_1^{\alpha_1 \rho_S \psi_1 + 1} y^{n_1} e^{(y-1)\left(\frac{\alpha_2}{\alpha_1 \rho_S \beta_{g2} y} - \frac{1}{\alpha_1 \rho_S \beta_{g3}}\right)} dy \quad (16) \\
 &= \alpha_1 \rho_S \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_1 \rho_S}\right)^\mu \sum_{n_1=0}^{\mu} \binom{\mu}{n_1} (-1)^{\mu-n_1} e^{\frac{\alpha_2}{\alpha_1 \rho_S \beta_{g2}} + \frac{1}{\alpha_1 \rho_S \beta_{g3}}} \\
 &\quad \times \int_1^{\alpha_1 \rho_S \psi_1 + 1} y^{n_1+1-1} e^{-\frac{\alpha_2}{\alpha_1 \rho_S \beta_{g2} y} - \frac{y}{\alpha_1 \rho_S \beta_{g3}}} dy.
 \end{aligned}$$

the inner integral can be solved by using result in [25, Eq. (3.381.1)] with $\mu \triangleq k + m_{g_3} - 1$ and:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Xi_2 &\triangleq \Pr(\gamma_{D_2 \rightarrow D_1} > \gamma_{th,2}) \\
 &= \Pr\left(|g_1|^2 > \frac{\gamma_{th,2}(\rho_1 |g_f|^2 + 1)}{\alpha_2 \rho_S - \alpha_1 \rho_S \gamma_{th,2}}\right) \\
 &= 1 - \sum_{n_1=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n_2=0}^{m_{g_1} + n_1} \binom{m_{h_1} + n_1}{n_2} \frac{(-1)^{n_1} \psi_1^{n_2} \psi_2^{m_{g_1} + n_1 - n_2} \Gamma(m_{g_f} + n_2)}{n_1! (m_{g_1} + n_1) \Gamma(m_{g_1}) \Gamma(m_{g_f})}.
 \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

next, Θ_2 can be calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Theta_2 &\triangleq \Pr(\gamma_{D_2 \rightarrow D_1} < \gamma_{th,2}, \gamma_{D_2,1} < \gamma_{th,2}) \\
 &= \underbrace{\Pr\left(|g_1|^2 < \frac{\gamma_{th,2}(\rho_{D_1} |h_f|^2 + 1)}{\alpha_2 \rho_S - \alpha_1 \rho_S \gamma_{th,2}}\right)}_{\triangleq \Xi_3} \times \underbrace{\Pr\left(|g_3|^2 < \frac{\gamma_{th,2}}{\alpha_2 \rho_S - \alpha_1 \rho_S \gamma_{th,2}}\right)}_{\triangleq \Xi_4},
 \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

in which,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Xi_3 &\triangleq \Pr\left(|g_1|^2 < \frac{\gamma_{th,2}(\rho_1 |g_f|^2 + 1)}{\alpha_2 \rho_S - \alpha_1 \rho_S \gamma_{th,2}}\right) \\
 &= \int_0^{\frac{\gamma_{th,2}(\alpha_3 \rho_1 y + 1)}{\alpha_2 \rho_S - \alpha_1 \rho_S \gamma_{th,2}}} \int_0^{\infty} f_{|g_1|^2}(x) f_{|g_f|^2}(y) dx dy \\
 &= \int_0^{\infty} \sum_{n_3=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n_4=0}^{m_{g_1} + n_3} \binom{m_{g_1} + n_3}{n_4} \frac{(-1)^{n_3} \omega_3^{n_4} \omega_4^{\mu_1} x^{n_4}}{n_3! (m_{g_1} + n_3) \Gamma(m_{g_1})} f_{|g_f|^2}(x) dx \\
 &= \sum_{n_3=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n_4=0}^{m_{g_1} + n_3} \binom{m_{g_1} + n_3}{n_4} \frac{(-1)^{n_3} \Gamma(m_{g_f} + n_4)}{n_3! (m_{g_1} + n_3) \Gamma(m_{g_1}) \Gamma(m_{g_f})} \\
 &\quad \times \left(\frac{\gamma_{th,2}}{\alpha_2 \rho_S - \alpha_1 \rho_S \gamma_{th,2}}\right)^{n_4} \left(\frac{\gamma_{th,2}}{\rho_1}\right)^{\mu_1},
 \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

where $\mu_1 = m_{g_1} + n_3 - n_4$:

$$\begin{aligned} \Xi_4 &\triangleq \Pr \left(|g_3|^2 < \frac{\gamma_{th,2}}{\alpha_2 \rho_S - \alpha_1 \rho_S \gamma_{th,2}} \right) \\ &= 1 - e^{-\frac{\gamma_{th,2}}{(\alpha_2 \rho_S - \alpha_1 \rho_S \gamma_{th,2}) \beta_{g_3}}} \sum_{n_5=0}^{m_{g_3}-1} \frac{1}{n_5!} \left(\frac{\gamma_{th,2}}{(\alpha_2 \rho_S - \alpha_1 \rho_S \gamma_{th,2}) \beta_{g_3}} \right)^{n_5} \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

based on (19) and (20), we have (21).

$$\begin{aligned} \Theta_2 &= \Xi_3 \times \Xi_4 \\ &= \sum_{n_3=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n_4=0}^{m_{g_1}+n_3} \binom{m_{g_1}+n_3}{n_4} \frac{(-1)^{n_3} \Gamma(m_{g_f} + n_4)}{n_3! (m_{g_1} + n_3) \Gamma(m_{g_1}) \Gamma(m_{g_f})} \\ &\quad \times \left(\frac{\gamma_{th,2}}{\alpha_2 \rho_S - \alpha_1 \rho_S \gamma_{th,2}} \right)^{n_4} \left(\frac{\gamma_{th,2}}{\rho_1} \right)^{\mu_1} \\ &\quad \times \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\gamma_{th,2}}{(\alpha_2 \rho_S - \alpha_1 \rho_S \gamma_{th,2}) \beta_{g_3}}} \sum_{n_5=0}^{m_{g_3}-1} \frac{1}{n_5!} \left(\frac{\gamma_{th,2}}{(\alpha_2 \rho_S - \alpha_1 \rho_S \gamma_{th,2}) \beta_{g_3}} \right)^{n_5} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

3.3. Throughput

The throughput is further metric to evaluate a system can be implemented effectively or not. In fact, it depends to outage probability and target rates, so it could be examined as follow. The throughput of D_1 and D_2 are given by:

$$\mathcal{E}_{D_1} = (1 - \mathcal{OP}_{D_1}^{DL}) \times R_1 \quad (22)$$

and,

$$\mathcal{E}_{D_2} = (1 - \mathcal{OP}_{D_2}^{DL}) \times R_2 \quad (23)$$

the overall system throughput is given by (24).

$$\mathcal{E}_{\text{system}} = \mathcal{E}_{D_1} + \mathcal{E}_{D_2} \quad (24)$$

4. NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this section, we perform Matlab simulations to verify derived expressions above. Some general parameters as $\lambda_{g_1} = d^{-\alpha}$, $\lambda_{g_2} = (1-d)^{-\alpha}$, $\lambda_{g_3} = 1$. Figure 2 depicts outage probability versus the transmit SNR at the BS. It can be seen that the significant improvement of outage behavior of two users is reported at high SNR region. Regarding quality of channels, $m = 5$ is known as the best case. The second user D_2 shows better outage performance compared with another user. Figure 3 shows the impact of quality of channel on outage probability. We see that the higher transmit SNR at the BS leads to improvement in term of outage probability. It can be seen that the limitation of outage performance happens as $\alpha = 5$ is known as the best case. The second user D_2 shows better outage performance compared with another user. Figure 4 shows the throughput of two users and the whole system. Since the throughput depends on outage probability, the highest throughput can be seen at high SNR region. Figure 5 indicates the impact of self-interference channel regarding on FD mode on the outage performance. Since the computation of SINR depends on such level of self-interference channel, the best performance can be reported at case of $\lambda_{g_f} = 0.001$.

Figure 2. Outage probability transmit SNR with $\alpha = 2, \alpha_1 = 0.4, d = 0.5, \lambda_{gf} = 0.01, R_1 = 2, R_2 = 0.75$

Figure 3. Outage probability with $R_1 = 2, R_2 = 0.75, \alpha_1 = 0.4, d = 0.5, \lambda_{gf} = 0.01, m = 3$

Figure 4. Throughput of two users and system throughput with $R_1 = 3, R_2 = 1, \alpha = 2, \alpha_1 = 0.3, d = 0.5, \lambda_{gf} = 0.01$

Figure 5. The system performance with different channel gains $R_1 = 1$, $R_2 = 0.75$, $\alpha = 3$, $\alpha_1 = 0.4$, $d = 0.5$, $\lambda_{gf} = 0.01$, $m = 2$

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have considered a downlink FD based NOMA systems to exploit outage performance. In particular, the system metric is improved by employing better channel parameters along with low level of self-interference channel condition due to FD mode. We derived exact expressions of outage probability and then the throughput is also presented. We presented simple model of FD for the BS serve two NOMA users. We extend to multiple antennas designed at the BS to improve performance in the future work.

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